

A General Approach

to the Mechanics of Composite Materials

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1 Introduction

It has been felt for years that the mechanical behaviour of a real engineering material which may very often be interpreted as a composite material, can well be described by some system of simple rheological models.

This intuitive approach leans usually on mere analogy and fails to connect the individual rheological members in the system with the specific kinds of microparticles existing in the material. The reason probably lies in the fact that such a connection is very difficult to effect precisely: in the real microstructure, the scatter of the mechanical properties is very high, individual particles are anisotropic and with different orientation, the boundaries are apt to be not sharp, the plastic deformation is often concentrated in small regions only, and on top of all the above, the microparticles are in fact no particles of a continuum.

Another difficulty arises in connection with the

problem of how to arrange the members of the rheological model in the system. It is quite clear that they should be arranged somewhere between a parallel and a series model, or in other words, between homogeneous strain and homogeneous stress, but it is desirable that this should be done in a simple way and the transition made possible from one extreme to the other in dependence on the structure of the material under consideration.

The main ideas of the approach to be presented in this paper are as follows: to take advantage of the simple constitutive equations which are well known and elaborated, to use them as averaged characteristics for the material constituents, and to combine the constitutive equations of the material constituents in a special way that will be outlined subsequently, where specific material parameters indicate the "measure" to which the process approaches homogeneous stress or homogeneous strain. These parameters are determined from macroscopic tests performed on specimens of the composite.

In his earlier papers (cf. [7] to [11]) the author published various partial results of the theory and comparisons with experimental evidence. The present paper offers a newly deduced, formulated and completed theoretical basis of the approach.

2 Basic relations

Let us consider a two-phase quasihomogeneous composite material with some internal geometry and some constitutive equations of the material constituents.

The following relations are basic for such a material:

$$(2.1) \quad v_a^r \sigma_{ija} + v_b^r \sigma_{ijb} = \bar{\sigma}_{ij}$$

$$(2.2) \quad v_a^* \varepsilon_{ija} + v_b^* \varepsilon_{ijb} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}$$

$$(2.3) \quad \overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}} = \overline{\sigma_{ij}} \overline{\varepsilon_{ij}}$$

where σ_{ij} , ε_{ij} are the stress- and strain-tensors, respectively, v_a^* ($= 1 - v_b^*$) is the volume fraction of the a - material constituent, $\overline{\sigma_{ija}}$ is the arithmetic mean of σ_{ij} in the a - material, and $\overline{\sigma_{ij}}$ is the arithmetic mean of σ_{ij} in the composite.

The above equations were deduced and discussed from many points of view in papers [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [7]. Let us mention that they hold equally good for the rates or differentials of the respective quantities, and by linear combination of eqs. (2.1) or (2.2) it can easily be shown that they are also valid for deviatoric and volumetric parts separately.

As to eq. (2.3): we see that

$$(2.3)' \quad \begin{aligned} \overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}} &= \overline{S_{ij} e_{ij}} + 3 \overline{\sigma} \overline{\varepsilon} = \\ &= \overline{\sigma_{ij}} \overline{\varepsilon_{ij}} = \overline{S_{ij}} \overline{e_{ij}} + 3 \overline{\sigma} \overline{\varepsilon} \end{aligned}$$

where S_{ij} , e_{ij} are the deviatoric parts, and σ, ε are the thirds of the respective first invariants.

The equation

$$(2.4) \quad \overline{S_{ij} e_{ij}} = \overline{S_{ij}} \overline{e_{ij}}$$

is valid under the restriction that the deviatoric or the volumetric micro-quantities are caused by their macroscopic counterparts only. Such cases arise, e.g. when the volume changes are zero throughout the composite material, or - in an elastic-plastic process - when the plastic volume change is zero, the elastic moduli are constant in the composite, and the process is isothermal or the coefficient of thermal expansion constant. For the last-named particular case eq. (2.4) follows

from the fact that the elastic solution gives $\sigma = \bar{\sigma}$ in the composite, and there exist no other causes to create residual values of σ .

Eq. (2.2) is valid for total strain. It applies separately to elastic and plastic parts only in the case when the elastic moduli are constant in the composite (cf. [3], [4], [5], [7]).

It follows further from eq. (2.3) that

$$(2.5) \quad \overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}} = \psi_a (\overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}})_a + \psi_b (\overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}})_b$$

where $(\overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}})_a$ is the arithmetic mean of $(\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij})$ in the microparticles of the a - material constituent.

Let us emphasize at this point that

$$(\overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}})_a \neq \overline{\sigma_{ija} \varepsilon_{ija}}$$

contrary to eq. (2.3). The equality in (2.3) follows namely from the divergence theorem and Saint Venant's principle which may be applied to a continuous part of the composite material but cannot be applied to particles of a material constituent.

Let us furthermore accept the fundamental theorem of the "theories with internal variables" according to which the current state of a material may be described by a finite number of variables. Applying this theorem to a composite we may postulate that $\overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}}$ can be expressed as a function of certain variables (the internal variables being included); accordingly, the expression

$$(2.6) \quad \Pi(X_k) = \overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}} - \overline{\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}} = 0$$

is also a function of such a type, with the property that it equals zero throughout any possible process.

It follows that any variation of Π equals zero:

$$\delta \Pi = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial X_k} \delta X_k = 0$$

(summation over $k, k=1, \dots, N$)

where N is the number of the variables X_k .

Let us further assume that using all the constraints to which the variables are subjected, we have eliminated some of them and have thus reduced their number to only that of the independent variables. Consequently, the function $\pi(X_k)$ will change to another form which we denote by

$$\pi'(X_l) \quad (l=1, \dots, n)$$

where $n (< N)$ is the number of the independent variables.

On the strength of the above we have

$$(2.7) \quad \delta \pi' = \frac{\partial \pi'}{\partial X_l} \delta X_l = 0 \quad \text{for any } \delta X_l$$

or

$$(2.8) \quad \frac{\partial \pi'}{\partial X_l} = 0 \quad (l=1, \dots, n)$$

The number of applicable constraints valid beforehand was $(N-n)$, and with n equations (2.8) there becomes available a system of N equations for N unknowns.

3 Supplementary assumptions

Let us define a small macroscopic neighbourhood of a point as a neighbourhood characterized by that it is small as regard the changes of macroscopic stress and macroscopic strain, and large as regard the dimensions of the microparticles. Hence macroscopic stress and macroscopic strain may be considered to be homogeneous in that neighbourhood, and as the material is also assumed to be macroscopically homogeneous, with such qualifications, all macroscopic sections through the neighbourhood will be equivalent as to the distribution of any quantity, any average value in such a section will equal the respective average value in the volume, and hence any section may be chosen as representative of the distribution in the volume.

Now, if such a plane section is drawn through the material, it will intersect the microparticles of one material kind in microsections of different shapes and sizes. Imagine further that the micro-sections through the chosen material constituent are subdivided into areas of still lesser order of magnitude; as a result the courses of a certain quantity in those areas will be brought close together to form a circle the radius of which is chosen as unity, and the areas will be arranged in such a way that the quantity being examined forms an axially symmetric configuration above the circle. This can always be done - without any supposition needed.

In the discussion that follows we shall accept two simplifying assumptions concerning the distribution above the circular area:

Assumption I: "In a material constituent, any component of strain-increment, stress-increment or stress deviates from the respective macroscopic average in one direction only, i.e. it is everywhere larger or everywhere smaller".

The exceptions to this rule are assumed to have a character of random deviations compensated by random deviations of opposite direction so that their integral manifestation is negligible.

Assumption II: "(i) The axial section of the axially symmetric deterministic distribution may be approximated by a power function.
(ii) The corresponding values of strain-increment, stress and stress-increment lie at the same distance from the axis in their respective distributions.
(iii) The exponents in the distribution functions are material constants of the

composite, generally different for different material constituents and for different components of the respective tensors".

If a chosen material constituent is, for example, less resistant to deformation than the macroscopic average, the deviations of the strain-increments from the macroscopic average will be to larger values and those of stress to smaller values. The periphery of the circle describes the situation at the contact surfaces causing the strongest constraint, and the strain-increment attains there its minimum equal to the macroscopic strain-increment. As the distance from the periphery grows larger, the influence of the constraint exerted at the contact surfaces grows weaker and the maximum is attained at the centre of the circle.

Similarly, the value of stress or stress-increment attains its maximum - the macroscopic stress - at the centre of the distribution where the influence of the constraint is weakest, for without the constraint exerted by another material of different properties, the value would equal the macroscopic stress throughout the chosen material constituent. On the periphery of the circle the constraint is maximal, corresponding to the homogeneous macroscopic deformation, and accordingly, the value of stress is minimal.

In mathematical terms the above assumptions applied to the n -th material constituent may be expressed as follows:

$$(3.1) \quad \begin{aligned} d\varepsilon_{ij} &= d\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} + x^{p_n} da_{ij} \\ \sigma_{ij} &= \sigma_{ijn}^* + x^{q_n} b_{ij} \\ d\sigma_{ij} &= d\sigma_{ijn}^* + x^{r_n} dc_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

$$p_n \geq 0, \quad q_n \geq 0, \quad r_n \geq 0$$

where X is the distance from the circular periphery (see Fig. 1), ϵ_{ij} , σ_{ij} are the current values in the distribution, σ_{ijn}^* is the value of σ_{ij} on the periphery corresponding to the homogeneous macroscopic deformation constraint, $\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$ the macroscopic deformation, da_{ij} , b_{ij} , dc_{ij} are some parameters of the distribution undergoing a change in the course of the process, and p_n , q_n , r_n are the positive exponents of the distribution - the material constants.

Fig. 1

In the n -th material constituent the arithmetic means of the quantities whose distribution is given by (3.1) may be expressed as follows:

$$(3.2) \quad d\epsilon_{ijn} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 2\pi(1-x) (d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} + x^{p_n} da_{ij}) dx$$

$$\sigma_{ijn} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 2\pi(1-x) (\sigma_{ijn}^* + x^{2n} b_{ij}) dx$$

$$d\sigma_{ijn} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 2\pi(1-x) (d\sigma_{ijn}^* + x^{2n} dc_{ij}) dx$$

Similarly, the increment of internal work on unit area (representative of unit volume) is defined by

$$(3.3) \quad (\overline{\sigma_{\alpha\beta} d\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}})_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 2\pi(1-x) \sigma_{\alpha\beta} d\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta} dx =$$

$$= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 2\pi(1-x) (\sigma_{\alpha\beta n}^* + x^{2n} b_{\alpha\beta}) \underbrace{(d\bar{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta} + x^{2n} d\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta})}_{\text{(no summation)}} dx$$

On taking the integrals in (3.2) and (3.3) we can easily deduce that

$$(\overline{\sigma_{\alpha\beta} d\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}})_n = \sigma_{\alpha\beta n} d\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta n} + \frac{1}{\eta_n} \sigma'_{\alpha\beta n} d\varepsilon'_{\alpha\beta n}$$

(no summation)

and for all components:

$$(3.4) \quad (\overline{\sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}})_n = \sigma_{ijn} d\varepsilon_{ijn} + \xi_{ijn} d\varepsilon'_{ijn}$$

(summation over i, j ; no summation over n)

where we have used the following notation:

$$(3.5) \quad \sigma'_{ijn} = \sigma_{ijn} - \sigma_{ijn}^*$$

$$(3.6) \quad d\varepsilon'_{ijn} = d\varepsilon_{ijn} - d\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}$$

$$(3.7) \quad \eta_n = \frac{2}{p_n q_n} \cdot \frac{p_n^2 + q_n^2 + 2p_n q_n + 3p_n + 3q_n + 2}{p_n q_n + 3p_n + 3q_n + 5}$$

(no summation)

$$(3.8) \quad \xi_{\alpha\beta n} = \frac{\sigma'_{\alpha\beta n}}{\eta_{\alpha\beta n}}$$

The symbol $\eta_{\alpha\beta n}$ newly introduced into the last equation has the meaning of η_n for the $\alpha\beta$ -components, as it may differ for different components.

By Assumption II, $\eta_{\alpha\beta n}$ are material constants and the physical meaning of eq. (3.4) is simple: the increment of internal work in unit volume of a material constituent is expressed as the sum of two terms, the first describing the work of the arithmetic means (overcoming the resistance of microparticles to the average strain), the second defining the work of the differential deformation in regard to the macroscopic average (overcoming the resistance of microparticles of a material kind to being deformed differently than the surrounding neighbourhood to which they are constrained on the contact surfaces).

Consulting Fig. 1 and eq. (3.1) we can readily deduce that $p_n \rightarrow 0$, $q_n \rightarrow 0$, $r_n \rightarrow 0$ ($\Rightarrow \eta_n \rightarrow \infty$) leads to homogeneous stress ($\sigma_{ijn} = \bar{\sigma}_{ij}$, $d\sigma_{ijn} = d\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$), and $p_n \rightarrow \infty$, $q_n \rightarrow \infty$, $r_n \rightarrow \infty$ ($\Rightarrow \eta_n \rightarrow 0$) leads to homogeneous strain ($d\epsilon_{ijn} = d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$ throughout the process).

The above may also be shown in a different way: using eq. (3.4) in (2.5) (modified for incremental strain) we obtain

$$(3.9) \quad \bar{\sigma}_{ij} d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \bar{\sigma}_{ij} d\epsilon_{ij} = \sum_{n=a,b} v_n^h (\sigma_{ijn} d\epsilon_{ijn} + \xi_{ijn} d\epsilon'_{ijn})$$

The constraints to which $d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$, $d\epsilon_{ijn}$, $d\epsilon'_{ijn}$ are bound, are equations (2.2) and (3.6), and by using them we can eliminate $d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$, $d\epsilon'_{ijn}$. Having done so we can use expression (3.9) in eq. (2.7) and obtain

$$(3.10) \quad \delta \Pi' = v_a^h v_b^h (\sigma_{ija} - \sigma_{ijb} + \xi_{ija} - \xi_{ijb}) \cdot (d\epsilon_{ija} - d\epsilon_{ijb}) = 0$$

and by eq. (2.8) and (3.8):

$$(3.11) \quad \sigma_{\alpha\beta a} - \sigma_{\alpha\beta b} + \frac{\sigma'_{\alpha\beta a}}{\eta_{\alpha\beta a}} - \frac{\sigma'_{\alpha\beta b}}{\eta_{\alpha\beta b}} = 0$$

Considering now eq. (3.11) we see that $\eta_{\alpha\beta a} \rightarrow \infty$, $\eta_{\alpha\beta b} \rightarrow \infty$ leads to

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta a} = \sigma_{\alpha\beta b}$$

or, by Assumption I and eq. (2.1), to homogeneous stress component $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}$ in the composite.

On the other hand, if $\eta_{\alpha\beta a} \rightarrow 0$, $\eta_{\alpha\beta b} \rightarrow 0$, the necessary condition for the fulfilment of eq. (3.11) is

$$\sigma'_{\alpha\beta a} = \sigma_{\alpha\beta a} - \sigma_{\alpha\beta a}^* = 0$$

$$\sigma'_{\alpha\beta b} = \sigma_{\alpha\beta b} - \sigma_{\alpha\beta b}^* = 0$$

which means that the stress components in the a - constituent differ from those in the b - constituent but are homogeneous within a material constituent and correspond to the homogeneous macroscopic deformation constraint $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \bar{\epsilon}_{\alpha\beta}$.

4 Constitutive equations

So far we have made no assumptions as to the constitutive equations of the material constituents.

Now we shall admit that the constitutive equations in any material constituent may be expressed in the form

$$(4.1) \quad \begin{aligned} de_{ij} &= A_n ds_{ij} + s_{ij} dB_n \\ d\epsilon &= C_n d\sigma \end{aligned}$$

where A_n , dB_n , C_n may be very general, depend on different variables, vary in the course of the deformation process, and change from one macroscopic point to another; but they are constant within a material constituent in a small macroscopic neighbourhood of a point.

We shall assume that it is possible to describe the distribution of the deviatoric and the volumetric parts separately in a manner similar to that used when writing eq. (3.1) for the total components, with the parameters p_n , q_n , r_n possibly different and the restriction on A_n , dB_n , C_n meaning that the quantities are independent of χ . In the case of elastic deformation this has the significance of elastic homogeneity.

ty of a material constituent in a small macroscopic neighbourhood of a point. For plastic deformation this question will be clarified later on.

Using eq. (3.1) modified for the deviatoric components, in eq. (4.1) we obtain

$$(4.2) \quad d\bar{e}_{ij} + X^{p_n} da_{ij} = A_n (ds_{ijn}^* + X^{2n} db_{ij}) + (s_{ijn}^* + X^{r_n} c_{ij}) dB_n$$

The above equation must hold good for any X , and the necessary conditions to satisfy this requirement are

$$(4.3) \quad d\bar{e}_{ij} = A_n ds_{ijn}^* + s_{ijn}^* dB_n$$

$$(4.4) \quad p_n = q_n = r_n$$

With the properties assumed for A_n , dB_n , eq.(4.1) may readily be integrated to give the relation between the arithmetic means (cf. (3.2)):

$$(4.5) \quad de_{ijn} = A_n ds_{ijn} + s_{ijn} dB_n$$

Subtracting further eq. (4.5) from eq. (4.3) we have

$$(4.6) \quad de'_{ijn} = A_n ds'_{ijn} + s'_{ijn} dB_n$$

Quite analogously we can derive that

$$(4.7) \quad d\epsilon_n = C_n d\sigma_n \\ d\epsilon'_n = C_n d\sigma'_n$$

The meaning of equations (4.5), (4.6) and (4.7) is that we have formulated the constitutive equations of a material constituent in terms of the variables ϵ_{ijn} , ϵ'_{ijn} , σ_{ijn} , σ'_{ijn} which relate to a macroscopic point, express - according to eq. (3.4) - the internal work, and with the material constants $\eta_{\alpha\beta n}$ known, are sufficient to describe the distribution of internal microstresses and in turn the state of the material in the sense of the concept presented here.

5 A quasiisotropic elastic-plastic material

We shall now investigate a composite consisting of small particles of two material constituents whose geometry and distribution are not specified but are considered to be random so that macroscopically the composite is isotropic. In this case the parameters $\eta_{\alpha\beta n}$ are not different for different $\alpha\beta$ and therefore we can simply write η_n without the subscripts $\alpha\beta$.

5.1 Particular constitutive equations

Let us further restrict our considerations to the case when one constituent, (a), is elastic-plastic and its properties are described by the Prandtl-Reuss equations, and the other constituent, (b), remains elastic and hence its particles form obstacles to plastic deformation. The elastic compliances $\mu = (1+\nu)/E$, $\rho = (1-2\nu)/E$ and the coefficient of thermal expansion are assumed to be the same for both constituents.

This particular mathematical model is of the type referred to in Section 2, in which the deviatoric parts of stress and strain may be investigated separately from the first invariants, and eq. (2.4) holds true.

It follows that in this case all the considerations put forward in the foregoing sections, particularly in Section 2 can be repeated for the deviatoric parts separately.

Equation (4.1) will take on the following forms: for the first invariants in both material constituents:

$$(5.1) \quad d\epsilon = \rho d\sigma$$

for the deviatoric parts:

in the a - material constituent

$$de_{ij} = \mu ds_{ij} + s_{ij} d\lambda$$

in the b - material constituent

$$de_{ij} = \mu ds_{ij}$$

In the case in question the restriction that dB_n is independent of X in the distribution, analogous to eq. (3.1), means that the scalar measure of plastic deformation is taken constant in the a - material constituent in a small macroscopic neighbourhood of a point, or, in other words, that the increment of plastic deformation is proportional to the deviatoric stress. This, of course, implies an averaged description but anyhow, in reality the measures $d\lambda$ in the neighbouring micro-points of a material constituent are not independent and compared with the classical theories of plasticity where $d\lambda$ is constant in the whole macroscopic neighbourhood of a point, this is a step towards a more realistic description.

Equations (4.5) and (4.6) will take on the form

(5.2)

$$de_{ija} = \mu ds_{ija} + s_{ija} d\lambda$$

$$de'_{ija} = de_{ija} - d\bar{e}_{ij} = \mu ds'_{ija} + s'_{ija} d\lambda$$

$$de_{ijb} = \mu ds_{ijb}$$

$$de'_{ijb} = de_{ijb} - d\bar{e}_{ij} = \mu ds'_{ijb}$$

It follows from eqs. (5.2)₁, (5.2)₃, (2.2) and (2.1) that

$$(5.3) \quad d\bar{e}_{ij} = \mu d\bar{s}_{ij} + v_a^n s_{ija} d\lambda$$

The above equation states that the increment of macroscopic plastic deformation is proportional to the mean deviatoric stress S_{ija} in micro-particles which deform plastically, in contrast to the classical relation according to which it is proportional to the macroscopic deviatoric stress.

By combining eqs. (2.1), (2.2), (3.11), (5.2) writ-

ten for the deviatoric parts and differentiated, we can easily deduce that

$$(5.4) \quad ds_{ija} = d\bar{s}_{ij} - \frac{\nu_b}{\mu(\nu_a \eta_a + \nu_b \eta_b + \eta_a \eta_b)} \cdot \\ \cdot [(\nu_a \eta_a + \nu_b \eta_b) s_{ija} - \eta_b s'_{ija}] d\lambda$$

$$(5.5) \quad ds'_{ija} = \frac{\eta_a}{\mu(\nu_a \eta_a + \nu_b \eta_b + \eta_a \eta_b)} \cdot \\ \cdot [\nu_b \eta_b s_{ija} - (\nu_a + \eta_b) s'_{ija}] d\lambda$$

The other components of the microscopic stress, S_{ijb} , S'_{ijb} may be obtained from eqs. (2.1) and (3.11) or - more exactly still - from their modified form written for the deviatoric components.

In accordance with what was stated in Section 3 we may easily show that $\eta_a \rightarrow \infty$, $\eta_b \rightarrow \infty$ leads to homogeneous deviatoric stress, and $\eta_a \rightarrow 0$, $\eta_b \rightarrow 0$ to homogeneous deviatoric strain.

The first statement follows immediately from eq. (5.4) where we obtain

$$ds_{ija} = d\bar{s}_{ij}$$

throughout the process.

The second statement may be arrived at on the basis of eq. (5.5) which for a process starting from the virgin state ($s'_{ija} = s_{ija} = \bar{s}_{ij} = 0$) leads to

$$ds'_{ij} = 0$$

throughout the process, and as eqs. (5.2)₂ and (2.2) infer

$$de_{ija} = d\bar{e}_{ij} = de_{ijb}$$

5.2 Field criterion

In order to complete the macroscopic constitutive

equations it is necessary to express $d\lambda$ in terms of the increments of macroscopic stress. This can be done once the yield criterion is formulated.

In our concept the microscopic stress-state in the a - material is described by the tensors S_{ija} , S'_{ija} and therefore the yield criterion is formulated in terms of these quantities:

$$(5.6) \quad f(S_{ija}, S'_{ija}, k) = 0$$

where the plastic limit k may depend on temperature and f is negative in the elastic range.

By differentiation we obtain

$$(5.7) \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial S_{ija}} dS_{ija} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial S'_{ija}} dS'_{ija} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial T} dT = 0$$

(summation over i, j ; no summation over a)

If we substitute for dS_{ija} , dS'_{ija} from eqs. (5.4) and (5.5), the expression of $d\lambda$ turns out to be

$$(5.8) \quad d\lambda = \mu (\dot{v}_a \eta_a + \dot{v}_b \eta_b + \eta_a \eta_b) \ll \frac{\partial f}{\partial S_{ija}} d\bar{S}_{ij} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial T} dT \gg /$$

$$/ \left\{ \dot{v}_b \left[(\dot{v}_a \eta_a + \dot{v}_b \eta_b) S_{ija} - \eta_b S'_{ija} \right] \frac{\partial f}{\partial S_{ija}} - \right.$$

$$\left. - \eta_a \left[\dot{v}_b \eta_b S_{ija} - (\dot{v}_a + \eta_b) S'_{ija} \right] \frac{\partial f}{\partial S'_{ija}} \right\}$$

where - to distinguish between loading and unloading - we define

$$\ll X \gg = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad f \neq 0$$

$$\quad \quad \quad \text{or} \quad f = 0, \quad X \leq 0$$

$$\ll X \gg = X \quad \text{for} \quad f = 0, \quad X > 0$$

The following particular form of (5.6) now seems to be the most appropriate and well corresponding to experimental data:

$$(5.9) \quad f \equiv S_{ija} S_{ija} - 2k^2 - p S'_{ija} S'_{ija} = 0$$

where $\rho \geq 0$.

For $\rho = 0$, this would be the Mises criterion written for a material constituent. For $\rho \neq 0$, there is induced in the a - material constituent the intrinsic strain-hardening connected with the microscopic heterogeneity of stress and deformation. This connection seems to be natural, as homogeneous deformation on micro-scale may in fact be represented by translation of regular rows of atoms to one another, which leads to no changes in the relative configuration in the lattice and therefore to no changes in the resistance to deformation. On the other hand, microscopic heterogeneity of deformation and stress (describing statistically the distribution of interatomic forces) means disorder in the lattice and strain-hardening (cf. [11]).

However, this "intrinsic" strain-hardening in a material constituent is not the only cause of strain-hardening in the composite. The other, the most important cause is a result of interaction between the constituents and leads to the typical nonlinear stress-strain curve even for $\rho = 0$.

Now, what kind of changes of the macroscopic yield criterion will eq. (5.9) provide? To answer this question let us define

$$(5.10) \quad S_{ija}^r = S_{ija} - \bar{S}_{ij}$$

where S_{ija}^r is clearly the residual value of S_{ija} for elastic macroscopic unloading. The real unloading needs not necessarily be elastic and thus S_{ija}^r may be called the "ideal residual stress".

Taking account of (5.10) we may rewrite eq. (5.9) as follows:

$$(5.11) \quad f \equiv (\bar{S}_{ij} + S_{ija}^r)(\bar{S}_{ij} + S_{ija}^r) - 2k^2 - \rho S_{ija}^r S_{ija}^r = 0$$

(summation over i, j ; no summation over a)

For a virgin state where $S'_{ija} = 0$, $S'_{ija} = 0$, this means the Mises criterion on macro-scale, and plastic deformation leads to translation and enlargement of the hypersphere. Such changes of the original yield surface do not represent an exact description of experimental evidence which is very complicated and sensitive to the methods of experiment and definitions of the yield surface; however, they represent a reasonable approximation, especially if, as is done, the points of the yield surface are defined as intersections of the elastic straight line and backward extrapolation of a simple strain-hardening curve.

5.3 Normality

It is easy to show that the increment of macroscopic plastic deformation is normal to the yield surface (5.11).

The normal direction to the yield surface is

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{s}_{ij}} = 2(\bar{s}_{ij} + S'_{ija}) = 2s_{ija}$$

and when compared with eq. (5.3) shows agreement with the direction of the plastic strain-increment.

5.4 Uniqueness

Using the yield criterion (5.9) in eq. (5.8) we obtain

$$(5.12) \quad d\lambda = A \ll s_{ija} d\bar{s}_{ij} - \frac{\partial k^2}{\partial T} dT \gg$$

where we have used the following notation:

$$(5.13) \quad A = \mu (\dot{\nu}_a \eta_a + \dot{\nu}_b \eta_b + \eta_a \eta_b) / \left\{ \dot{\nu}_b^2 s_{ija} \cdot \right. \\ \cdot [(\dot{\nu}_a \eta_a + \dot{\nu}_b \eta_b) s_{ija} - \eta_b s'_{ija}] + \rho \eta_a s'_{ija} \cdot \\ \left. \cdot [\dot{\nu}_b \eta_b s_{ija} - (\dot{\nu}_a + \eta_b) s'_{ija}] \right\} = \mu (\dot{\nu}_a \eta_a + \dot{\nu}_b \eta_b + \eta_a \eta_b) /$$

$$[[\dot{v}_b (\dot{v}_a \eta_a + \dot{v}_b \eta_b) s_{ija} s_{ija} + \dot{v}_b \eta_b (p \eta_a - 1) s_{ija} s'_{ija} - p \eta_a (\dot{v}_a + \eta_b) s'_{ija} s'_{ija}]$$

In our concept (for details refer to [11]) the energy dissipation is described by

$$\dot{v}_a (s_{ija} s_{ija} + \frac{1}{\eta_a} s'_{ija} s'_{ija}) d\lambda$$

and therefore $d\lambda$ must be non-negative. We shall investigate the sufficient restriction on the yield criterion to ensure it.

The term with double brackets in (5.12) is non-negative by definition. A more complicated situation arises as regard the expression of A : It is clear from eq. (5.5) that for a simple proportional loading process from the virgin state it is

$$\text{sign}(s'_{ija}) = \text{sign}(s_{ija})$$

$$(\dot{v}_a + \eta_b) |s'_{ija}| \leq \dot{v}_b \eta_b |s_{ija}|$$

and because

$$\frac{\dot{v}_a \eta_a + \dot{v}_b \eta_b}{\eta_b} > \frac{\dot{v}_b \eta_b}{\dot{v}_a + \eta_b}$$

it also holds that

$$\eta_b |s'_{ija}| < (\dot{v}_a \eta_a + \dot{v}_b \eta_b) |s_{ija}|$$

Comparing the above inequalities with the first form of A , we may conclude that for a simple proportional loading process A is positive.

It further follows from eq. (5.9) that a unique value of $(s_{ija} s'_{ija})$ corresponds to a given value of $(s_{ija} s_{ija})$ on the yield surface, no matter what the trajectory of the process.

Now for fixed values of $(s_{ija} s_{ija})$ and $(s'_{ija} s'_{ija})$ the expression $(s_{ija} s'_{ija})$ attains its maximum if the respective components are proportional, as in the case of a simple proportional loading process.

The consequence of what has been said is that for a given value of $(s_{ija} s_{ija})$ on the yield surface, the

expressions $(s'_{ija} s'_{ija})$ and $(s_{ija} s'_{ija})$ cannot attain a higher value than they attain in the case of a proportional loading, in which case A is positive. It may therefore be concluded from the second form of A in eq. (5.13) that A is positive if:

or
 (5.14)
$$p \eta_a - 1 \leq 0$$

$$p \leq \frac{1}{\eta_a}$$

for in that case the subtracted term

$[v_b^p \eta_b (1 - p \eta_a) s_{ija} s'_{ija} + p \eta_a (v_a^p + \eta_b) s'_{ija} s'_{ija}]$
 is maximal for proportional loading where the positiveness is ensured.

With this question clarified it is easy to prove uniqueness by contradiction, proceeding similarly as in [6].

Let us suppose at first that for a given state of a body described by macroscopic quantities and microstresses, there exist two different fields of increments of macroscopic strain $d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}, d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^*$, with corresponding fields of incremental displacements du_i, du_i^* , and macroscopic stress $d\bar{\sigma}_{ij}, d\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^*$ satisfying the unique boundary conditions: prescribed increments of displacement on part S_n , and increments of tension on part S_t of the surface.

Then - owing to the unique boundary conditions being satisfied - the following equation must apply:

$$\int (d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} - d\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^*) (du_i - du_i^*) n_j dS = 0$$

and from this - by the divergence theorem -

$$\int (d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} - d\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^*) (d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} - d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^*) dV = \int l dV = 0$$

The integrated expression l may be given the following form:

$$l = (d\bar{s}_{ij} + \delta_{ij} d\bar{\sigma} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^* - \delta_{ij} d\bar{\sigma}^*)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \cdot (\mu d\bar{s}_{ij} + v_a^i s_{ija} A \ll s_{kla} d\bar{s}_{kl} - \frac{\partial k^2}{\partial T} dT \gg + \\
& + \delta_{ij} \rho d\bar{\sigma} - \mu d\bar{s}_{ij}^* - v_a^i s_{ija} A \ll s_{kla} d\bar{s}_{kl}^* - \frac{\partial k^2}{\partial T} dT \gg - \delta_{ij} \rho d\bar{\sigma}^*) = \\
& = 3\rho (d\bar{\sigma} - d\bar{\sigma}^*)^2 + \mu (d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*) \cdot \\
& \cdot (d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*) + v_a^i A (d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*) s_{ija} \cdot \\
& \cdot (\ll s_{kla} d\bar{s}_{kl} - \frac{\partial k^2}{\partial T} dT \gg - \ll s_{kla} d\bar{s}_{kl}^* - \frac{\partial k^2}{\partial T} dT \gg)
\end{aligned}$$

Let us denote the expressions in the first and second double brackets by X and X^* , respectively.

For $X > 0$, $X^* > 0$, the double brackets may be deleted and we have

$$\begin{aligned}
| & = 3\rho (d\bar{\sigma} - d\bar{\sigma}^*)^2 + \mu (d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*) (d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*) + \\
& + v_a^i A [s_{ija} (d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*)]^2
\end{aligned}$$

which means that $|$ is non-negative.

For $X > 0$, $X^* \leq 0$, we can write when expressing the above inequalities

$$s_{ija} d\bar{s}_{ij} > s_{ija} d\bar{s}_{ij}^*$$

hence in this case the following relations are valid:

$$(d\bar{s}_{ij} - d\bar{s}_{ij}^*) s_{ija} > 0$$

$$\ll X \gg > 0$$

$$\ll X^* \gg = 0$$

and $|$ is again non-negative.

We could proceed similarly when dealing with the other possible combinations of inequalities and show that $|$ is non-negative in every case and equal to zero only

for

$$d\bar{\sigma} = d\bar{\sigma}^*, \quad d\bar{s}_{ij} = d\bar{s}_{ij}^*, \quad d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^*$$

which implies that

$$d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = d\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^*, \quad d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = d\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^*$$

and uniqueness is thus established for increments of stress and strain.

6 Concluding remarks

In the particular mathematical model outlined in the preceding section, the constitutive equations of the material constituents are isotropic. This does not mean, however, that the material constituents which we describe must necessarily be isotropic on micro-scale. The description may be understood as averaged over the randomly distributed orientations. In that way the particular model can be applied to engineering polycrystalline materials where the obstacles (the b - material) are assumed to be concentrated mostly at the grain boundaries owing to impurities, precipitates and the change of orientation, an obstacle in itself.

In some earlier of author's papers [7], [8], [9], [11] such an application was compared with macroscopic behaviour of polycrystalline materials, with X-ray diffraction measurements of microstresses and with the measurements of stored energy, and a good agreement was found to exist between the data. The yield criterion used in the papers quoted above was somewhat different from that employed herein, but the principal results are found not to have been changed by that difference. The method of determining the material constants from macroscopic test data is outlined in paper [8] but - as will be shown in a forthcoming study - it may be improved for the criterion used in the present discussion.

The application of the general approach to fiber-reinforced materials is treated in [10].

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